

MAIN TYPES OF MEASUREMENTS IN PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract. *This article examines the basic concepts of mathematical statistics, describes groups of statistical methods used to process the results of a pedagogical experiment and form the listed competencies. Conclusions and recommendations for choosing certain statistical criteria when processing the results of an experiment are presented. The examination of the basic concepts of mathematical statistics and each statistical criterion ends with appropriate control questions. The article provides computer programs that allow statistical analysis of data in accordance with the nature of the tasks to be solved, the volume of data to be processed, the requirements for the user's qualifications, and the available computer equipment.*

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In the system of training specialists mastering master's programs in pedagogical and psychological-pedagogical fields, their ability to conduct relevant experiments in their future professional activity is of primary importance. Each dissertation research, an obligatory component of which is the experimental part, requires mastery of methods of statistical processing of experimental results.

At the same time, the national curriculum (NC) for the training program 70110501 "Psychological and Pedagogical Education" states that a graduate of the master's program must develop the following competencies: - the ability for abstract thinking, analysis, synthesis; - the ability to use scientifically based methods and technologies in psychological and pedagogical activities, to master modern technologies for organizing the collection, processing and interpretation of data; - the ability to design and carry out diagnostic work necessary in professional activities.

In the field of training "Pedagogical education" a graduate must have the ability to: - independently master and use new research methods, to master new areas of professional activity; - carry out professional and personal self-education, design further educational routes and a professional career; - apply modern methods and technologies for organizing educational activities, diagnostics and assessing the quality of the educational process in various educational programs; - analyze the results of scientific research, apply them in solving specific research problems in the field of science and education, independently carry out scientific research. One of the advantages of this manual is the examples of dissertation research using statistical methods of processing experimental data. The consideration of each statistical criterion ends with a corresponding task for work in class. It is worth noting the variety of tasks: - to identify errors in calculations or in the given logical reasoning according to a certain statistical method; - to consider various cases related to the application of the criterion under consideration and the corresponding methods of calculation for each of them, etc.

At the end of the article, there are assignments for independent work, including both theoretical and practical questions. In addition, the provided glossary is of interest, which helps the researcher work with the basic concepts of mathematical statistics and methods of processing the results of the psychological and pedagogical experiment. It should be noted that there are criteria for assessing the written and oral responses of students.

The concept of measurement. Types of measurement scales: Measurement is a procedure by which the measured object is compared with a certain standard and receives a numerical expression on a certain scale or on a special scale [3]. Psychological and pedagogical variables, with a few exceptions, do not have their own measurement units. Therefore, in most cases, the value of a psychological and pedagogical feature is determined using special measurement scales [5].

There are four types of measurement scales: 1) nominative, nominal, or name scale; 2) ordinal, ordinary, or rank scale; 3) interval, or equal interval scale; 3) equal ratio scale, or ratio scale. All the names in one line are synonyms and therefore will be used on an equal basis in the following presentation. In the process of conducting an experiment, the researcher can use the indicated methods, while it is necessary to note that each measurement scale has its own form of numerical representation, different from the others. When conducting an experiment, the researcher records the coded features of the phenomenon in a certain numerical system, which is determined by the characteristics of the scale used. Measurements are divided into qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative measurements are those that are carried out using the first two scales, and quantitative measurements are those that are carried out using the last two scales. Scales that lead to qualitative measurements are called discrete; scales that lead to quantitative measurements are called continuous [11].

Let us consider the scales listed above in detail. Nominative scale. Measurement in a nominative scale is expressed in the fact that a certain property or feature is assigned a corresponding designation or symbol (numerical, letter, etc.). In the process of measurement on this scale, a process of classification or distribution of objects into non-intersecting classes or groups occurs. A nominative scale indicates a qualitative difference from each other of certain properties or features, and any quantitative changes in them are not assumed. Thus, regarding the features measured on this scale, it is impossible to determine which of them is greater and which is less. It can only be stated that the features that fall into different groups are different, which characterizes this scale as qualitative. It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the symbols that are assigned to objects in the nominative scale are conditional and do not have defining information, while the operations carried out with them do not make sense. The simplest nominative scale is called dichotomous.

In the process of measurement on this scale, the studied features can be coded by two numbers or symbols, for example 1 and 0, or 6 and 2, or the letters C and D. Any symbols that differ from each other can be used. A feature measured on a dichotomous scale is called alternative. Note that in a dichotomous scale, all objects, features or properties under study must be divided into two non-overlapping classes, and the researcher must find an answer to the question of whether the feature of interest has manifested itself or not. The use of this scale allows the experimenter to identify the frequency of occurrence of the studied feature. When using a nominative scale, the unit of measurement is the number of observations. The total number of observations is taken as 100%, and the percentage is calculated. If there are more than two groups,

the percentage of subjects in each group can be calculated [4]. An example of measurement using a nominative scale can be the classification of students by the state of two features: gender and success in completing a test task.

In this case, two gradations are distinguished in the state of each feature: male/female and correct answer/incorrect answer. As a result, according to the state of two features, the group is divided into four classes: women who completed the task correctly; women who completed the task incorrectly; men who completed the task correctly; men who completed the task incorrectly. Next, we assign, for example, the number 1 to all objects of the first class, the number 2 to objects of the second class, the number 3 to objects of the third class, and the number 4 to objects of the fourth class. Classification of a certain set of objects by several features allows not only to identify the structure of the set, but also to obtain the data necessary to clarify the relationship between two or more features. In the given example, such features are the students' gender and the completion of the test task. It should be noted that only a small number of statistical methods (chi-square test, McNamara test, etc.) allow the presentation of results in the form of a nominative scale. For example, measurements on this scale are used to test certain statistical hypotheses, as well as to calculate the correlation indices of qualitative features [5].

Rank scale. Ranking rule Measurement on a rank scale divides the entire set of measured features into sets connected by relationships of the type “less – more”, “lower – higher”, “weaker – stronger”, etc. In a rank scale, all features are arranged by rank – from the largest to the smallest, from the strongest to the weakest, etc. When using a rank scale, there must be at least three classes for arranging the measured features in order. Therefore, the second name of this scale is “ordinal scale”. In the process of coding, any numbers or codes are assigned to ordinal variables, but it is necessary to pay attention to the mandatory presence of a certain order in the codes [6-7]. The ranking procedure is essentially formal, so the experimenter can, if desired, assign the rank values in the opposite order. For example, in the process of measuring the results of students' learning, the order scale can be represented by criteria that allow the results to be arranged according to the degree of increase or decrease of the studied feature. Thus, it is not possible to determine by what number of equal units in the state of the feature one object is greater or less than another. The order scale has a number of specific features.

Thus, the conclusions that were obtained by the experimenter using arithmetic operations with measurements performed on a given scale are affected by the choice of point estimates. In some cases, the conclusions may reflect not the objective properties of the phenomena under consideration, but random properties that are a consequence of the characteristic features of the adopted point estimate system. Using a measurement system on an order scale, it is necessary to remember the limitation: it is impossible to perform arithmetic operations with the numbers (points, ranks) assigned to objects - to calculate sums, find average values, dispersions, etc. [8]. The ranking procedure is quite simple. In the most general case, to check the correctness of the ranking of a column or row of features, the formula for the sum of all the obtained ranks is used: the measurements performed on a given scale are affected by the choice of point estimates. Thus, in some cases, the conclusions may reflect not the objective properties of the phenomena under consideration, but random properties that are a consequence of the characteristic features of the adopted point assessment system. Using a measurement system on an order scale, it is necessary to remember the limitation: with the numbers (points, ranks) assigned to objects, it is impossible to perform arithmetic operations - calculate sums, find average values, dispersions, etc. [11].

The ranking procedure is quite simple. In the most general case, to check the correctness of the ranking of a column or row of features, the formula for the sum of all the obtained ranks is used: Sum of ranks ,

Sum of ranks

$$1+2+3+\dots+=\frac{N\cdot(N+1)}{2}, \quad (1) \quad \frac{((k\cdot c+1)\cdot k\cdot c)}{2}, \quad (2)$$

$$= \frac{n\cdot c\cdot(c+1)}{2}, \quad (3)$$

Summing up the actual ranks, we also get the sum of the ranks equal to 55, which means the ranking is done correctly. A variety of statistical methods are applied to the experimental data obtained in this scale. Interval scale (1) where N is the number of ranked features. The coincidence of the results of calculating ranks according to the formula and according to the actual results of ranking the experimental data in this case will be a confirmation of the correctness of the ranking. In the case when the experimenter works with a table with a large number of rows and columns, when calculating ranks it is possible to use a modification of formula (1): the measurements performed according to this scale affect the choice of point estimates. Thus, in some cases the conclusions may reflect not the objective properties of the phenomena under consideration, but random properties that are a consequence of the characteristic features of the adopted point assessment system. When performing measurements, situations may arise when two or more qualities are assigned the same ranks. The same ranks can be assigned to any number of ranked quantities. In this case, they are also assigned the value of the arithmetic mean of the number of conditional ranks that were assigned in order of their values. When ranking quantitative characteristics, a special algorithm can be used. 1. The smallest numerical value is assigned a rank of 1.

2. The largest numerical value is assigned a rank that is equal to the number of values being ranked.

3. If several initial numerical values are equal, they are assigned a rank that corresponds to the average value of the ranks that these values would receive if they were in order one after another and were not equal. It should be noted that this case may include both the first and last values of the initial ranked series.

4. The total sum of real ranks should match the calculation formula (1) [11].

It should be noted that it is not recommended to rank more than 20 values (features, qualities, properties, etc.), since in this case the ranking becomes unstable. If there is a need to rank a large number of objects, then they should be combined according to the selected feature into homogeneous groups (classes), and then the formed groups (classes) should be ranked.

In an interval scale, or interval scale, each of the possible values of the measured quantities is equidistant from the nearest one.

The interval, which is the basic concept of this scale, is defined as the part or share of the measured property between two adjacent positions on the scale. The size of the interval is called a fixed and constant value on all sections of the scale.

Using an interval scale, special units of measurement are used in the measurement process. When working with this scale, the experimenter assigns a number to the measured property or object, which corresponds to the number of units of measurement and is equivalent to the amount of the existing property.

A characteristic feature of the interval scale is the absence of a natural reference point (zero is arbitrary and does not indicate the absence of the measured property) [10].

An interval scale, or a scale of equal units, is obtained by using a certain criterion, with the help of which it is possible to measure the interval between objects in the state of the property being studied, in other words, it is possible to find out by how many units one object is greater or less than another.

Depending on the nature of the problem under consideration by a given pedagogical science, one or another conditional zero level should be adopted. For example, when we evaluate students' performance of a task by the number of correct or incorrect answers to questions of a given task, then zero correct answers does not mean a complete absence of the knowledge tested by the task in this student. In pedagogy, with the exception of the time scale, which, although used quite widely, plays a special role in the theory of measurements, there are currently no interval-type measurement scales [3].

It should be noted that most statistical methods are used to obtain experimental data on an interval scale. The ratio scale is sometimes called the equal ratio scale. The characteristic feature of this scale is the presence of a fixed zero, denoting the complete absence of any property or feature. The ratio scale is the most informative scale, allowing the use of any mathematical operations and various statistical methods. Note the relative closeness of the ratio scale to the interval scale, since with strict fixation of the starting point, any interval scale is transformed into a ratio scale.

The process of transition from one scale of measurement to another (starting with the scale of names) is accompanied by an expansion of the class of mathematical operations and methods admissible for the obtained measurements. In this sense, the scale of relations is the best [11]. For a visual presentation of experimental data, various forms are used to facilitate the visual analysis of the information obtained in the experiment: tables, distribution series, graphs, histograms.

Processing of experimental data begins with the ordering and systematization of the collected data.

Grouping is understood as the process of systematizing the results of an experiment and combining them into relatively homogeneous groups according to a certain feature.

When conducting an experiment, grouping is not a standard technical method that allows you to present the original data in a different form, but an operation that allows you to understand the connections between the phenomena being studied.

Statistical tables are the most common form of grouping experimental data. They, in turn, are divided into simple and complex.

Simple tables include those that are used in alternative grouping, in the case of contrasting one group of subjects with another.

Researchers recommend using this type of table to record the results of an experiment in which the measurement of the studied features is carried out on a nominative or rank scale.

Complex tables include multi-field tables used by experimenters to clarify cause-and-effect relationships between varying features.

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